

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Du Plessis****FIRST NAME: Vincent****PROGRAM CODE: MBASD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did not use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MS Office 365

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **If one applied the ISO 8601 Standard for presenting dates, which of the following options would be the correct format to write 5 March 1912?**
 - March 5th, 1912
 - 1912-03-05¹
 - 05/03/12
 - 03.05.12

¹ Euclid University (a). 2015. ACA401 Coursepack: Period 1. Euclid University, 59.

2. **When employing the Chicago Manual of Style indicate the true statement about the writing of numbers.**

- In nontechnical contexts round numbers, numbers one to one hundred and numbers beginning a sentence are spelt out.²**
- Numbers from one to ten are always spelt out, even in technical contexts.
- When using numbers and units “52 degrees Celsius” is acceptable as Chicago style makes an exception for temperature measurements.
- When two numbers occur in the same sentence, it is better to present both as numerals, or both spelt out to avoid any confusion.

3. **Which of the following describes the best way to support your thesis when writing an academic paper?**

- Use logic and empirical evidence to argue your point.
- Analyse or examine different viewpoints on the subject.
- The type of support employed will depend on the subject of the paper, and one may employ more than one way to support the thesis.³**
- Compare your findings with previous research to draw a conclusion.

² Euclid University (a), 69.

³ Sebranek, Patrick, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer. 1999. Write Source 2000, A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning. Wilmington, MA: Great Source Education Group, 64.

4. **Which of the following statements is false?**

- Semicolons are used to join two independent sentences instead of using a coordinate conjunction.
- In formal writing, apostrophes can be used to indicate that one or more letter has been left out of a word to form a contraction.**⁴
- A hyphen can be used to add prefixes to words that otherwise might have a different meaning.
- In American usage, commas and full stops are always placed inside of the quotation marks.

5. **In Turabian Rule of Style, which of the following is the correct reference for the book.**

- Mandela, Nelson. 1995. *Long Walk to Freedom: The Autobiography of Nelson Mandela*. Back Bay Books: New York.
- Mandela, Nelson. 1995. Long Walk to Freedom: The Autobiography of Nelson Mandela. New York: Back Bay Books.
- Mandela, Nelson. *Long Walk to Freedom: The Autobiography of Nelson Mandela*. New York: Back Bay Books. 1995.
- None of the above**

⁴ Sebranek, Patrick, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, 402.

6. In Turabian style, which of the following statements are true with regards to the use of direct quotations.

- A direct quote spanning more than five lines must appear in a separate, indented block.⁵
- Direct quotes require the use the of quotation marks, and the text must appear in italics.
- The grammar of the direct quote is of no consequence and should not be integrated into the grammar of the writer.
- For quotations within quotations, the inner quotation must be indicated with quotation marks.

7. When using the Harvard Referencing Style, the correct way to write the reference for a book would be.

- Mandela, N. (1995) *Long Walk to Freedom: The Autobiography of Nelson Mandela*, New York: Back Bay Books.**⁶
- Mandela, Nelson. 1995. *Long Walk to Freedom: The Autobiography of Nelson Mandela*. Back Bay Books: New York.
- Mandela, N. 1995. Long Walk to Freedom: The Autobiography of Nelson Mandela. Back Bay Books: New York.
- Mandela, Nelson (1995) *Long Walk to Freedom: The Autobiography of Nelson Mandela*. New York: Back Bay Books.

⁵ Turabian, 208.

⁶ Euclid University (b). 2015. ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4. Euclid University, 81.

8. **When writing a research paper, there are several types of irrelevant information that should be avoided. Which of the following options is an example of irrelevant information?**
- Details on how the research team came to decide on the subject of their paper.
 - Defining photosynthesis to an audience of plant pathologists.
 - You are providing insight into your feeling on the ability of an economy to recover from a recession.
 - All of the above.**⁷
9. **You are reviewing a paper written by a student. Which sentence would you point out to them as having a mistake?**
- The results are dependant on several factors.
 - The subject remained stationery for two minutes.**⁸
 - The facility obtained an air emissions licence in 2009.
 - This practice started shortly after an incident recorded in 1823.

⁷ Euclid University (b), 8.

⁸ European Commission Directorate-General for Translation. 2011. English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission. Edited by Tim Cooper, John Fallas, Francis Flaherty, John Jones, Tim Martin, Jonathan Stockwell, Julia Townsend and Peter Workman. Luxembourg: European Commission Directorate-General for Translation, 7.

10. **You were recently appointed in a position with the European Commission. Which of the following should you avoid?**

- You request someone to assist the police officer in reception.
- You write a memo to female co-worker addressing her as Ms Johnshon.
- You send a group email indicating that the chairman requests agenda items for the next committee meeting.⁹**
- You ask a co-worker to ask the new secretary (that you have never met) to bring their notebook.

⁹ European Commission Directorate-General for Translation, 47.

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Sebranek, Patrick, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer. *Write Source 2000, A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning*. Wilmington, MA: Great Source Education Group, 1999.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne Booth, Gregory Colomb, Joseph Williams, and University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. Eighth. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.